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AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI SOHASI UCHUN KADRLAR

**USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING
TRANSLATION**

Abdukarimova Dildora Rakhmatullayevna

Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan

dildoraabdukarimova47@gmail.com

Annotation: This research work aims at showing problems of translation in teaching and focuses on dealing with these problems via implementing a number of interactive games and activities in the classroom using technology in terms of computers, e-readers, ppt presentations, and dubbing scripts.

Key words: computer, power point, podcasts, web quests, online games, translation activities, dubbing scenes and etc.

Technology is irrefutably, a great asset in ESL classrooms, offering authentic writing activities and endless recourses on grammar instructions, lesson plans and other central topics. It goes without saying that its role in translation activities is also requisite in our fast-moving education world. Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source –language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. Its role in English language teaching is considered as indispensable. Translation was a significant part of ELT for a long time, and then a significant missing part for a long time, as well. Translation was the basis of language teaching for a very long time, and then rejected as new methodologies started to appear. It was a key element of the Grammar Translation Method, which was derived from the classical method of teaching Greek and Latin[1]. This was not a positive learning experience for many: as well as learners memorizing huge lists of rules and vocabulary, this method involved them translating whole literary or historic texts word for word[2]. Unsurprisingly, new methodologies tried to improve on this. The Direct or Natural Method established in Germany and France around 1900 was a response to the obvious problems associated with the Grammar Translation Method. In the Direct Method the teacher and learners avoid using the learners’ native language and just use the target language[3]. Like the Direct Method, the later Audio-Lingual Method tried to teach the language directly, without using source language to explain new items. Subsequent “humanistic” methodologies, such as, the Silent Way and

Total Physical Response and communicative approaches moved even further away from the native language and from these arise many of the objections to translation. Translation encourages learners to use mother tongue, often for long periods of class time, when the aim of modern teaching is to remove it from the classroom. The skills involved in translation may not be suitable for all kinds of learners. It may, for example, be best for the learners who are analytical or have preference for verbal-linguistic learning strategies. It may not be suitable either for young learners or lower levels. Learners may not see the value of translation as an activity to help them learn English, and instead, they consider it as a difficult activity[4].

Translation activities are not easy to do, they need a lot of preparation. Teacher himself should have a sophisticated knowledge of both target language and source language. Without this, translation may create more problems than benefits. Translation is time-consuming task, but the teacher must be as good as and better than the learners in order to be able to manage the activity well[5].

1) Translation in groups are more beneficial than individual or pair-work translation activities. In groups learners discuss the meaning and use of language at the deepest possible levels as they work through the process of understanding and then looking for equivalents in another language. For example: the word “to understand” meaning “tushunmoq” in uzbek has a number of synonyms in English, such as, “to get”, “to comprehend”, “to perceive”, “to grasp”, “to make out” and so forth. If a teacher prepares an activity directed to enhance his students vocabulary range together with translation it will much more attention-grabbing lesson for learners. In such interesting educational classes devoted to learning translation, smart boards, which are really sophisticated tools, help to organize more effective lessons. At a time students of both groups can use it as a dictionary and blackboard, as well.

2) Discussion of differences and similarities during the translation process helps learners understand the interaction of the two languages and the problems caused by their native language. It also facilitates learners to compare both strength and weaknesses in both languages. The point aforementioned above can be seen in phraseological translation. For example, “you look like a million dollars” means you look gorgeous and cannot be translated word-for-word into uzbek. It is translated as “sizning ko’rinishingiz ajoyib”[7]. Teaching such problematic ways of translation as an interesting activity is up to teacher’s logical thinking. An activity can be held as paper-based, but of course, it will provoke students attention more if an explanation is given via video dialogue.

3) One of the effective ways to teach translation via activities is that, learners bring examples of first language (in their own language), or L2(in

another language) for discussion and translation. This can also be done as sharing materials. Learners translate and then other learners back translate, then compare versions and discuss why there are differences. Learners analyze “bad” translations and discuss the causes of errors[5]. Learners should find different kinds of texts for juxtaposition and translation, for example, recipes, e-mails, technical texts, announcements and etc. It can also be accomplished by traditional lesson, however, it is much easier to catch learners’ attention if the aforementioned activity is conducted by online games.

4) A teacher can organize project works with students. For example, learners translate the script from a film, then dub over the scene itself with their new version in the target language and it is also an advantage of technology usage in class. Implementation such an advantageous artificial intelligence during the lesson will undoubtedly facilitate to encourage learners to better their translation skills[6].

To sum up, technology is not a magic wand that will solve all your problems. You anyway need to know how to teach a lesson and teaching translation using technology as a part of the communicative ELT classroom approach is still a controversial area and one that provokes strong opinions. It needs to be practiced under the supervision of the teacher. Learners should have a possibility to exchange their knowledge and compare their choices of words. Activities above are aimed at focusing on translation that are communicative and textual. Many teachers think that translation makes the student look backward at a text, rather than forwards towards a person. The easiest way to rectify this misconception, is to start translation activities from spoken interactions. If a learning atmosphere is created in the classroom, even lessons devoted to translation will be interesting and fun.

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